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Directing Art Projects in the System of Training the Future Manager of the Socio-Cultural Sphere

Abstract: *Introduction.* Modern transformational processes in the socio-cultural sphere are due to the rapid spread of technologies that shape the personality of the future specialist in art institutions of higher education in Ukraine. A specific feature of directing art projects is the ability to expand the range of a certain worldview, to create conditions for the effective acquisition of professional knowledge and skills in the training future managers of socio-cultural activities. *Purpose and methods.* The purpose of the article is to identify current trends in the use of directing art projects in the training managers for the socio-cultural sphere. The research used systematic and methodological-didactic approaches, methods of analysis and synthesis, comparison and empirical methods, which proposed the structure of the discipline in the relationship of its main elements and determinants. *Results.* The main results of the research are to substantiate the need to introduce the direction of art projects in the system training managers of socio-cultural activities and use modern directing technologies in the socio-cultural sphere. *Conclusions.* In conditions of a modern institution in higher education, scientific provisions on the importance of directing in the acquisition of professional knowledge and skills, which allow to addition, identify and form the value competencies and competitiveness of the future manager of socio-cultural activities. Promising in the future is the study of favorable environment of the institution higher education in which the formation of the future manager of socio-cultural activities by way of directing art projects.

Keywords: project, socio-cultural activity, management of socio-cultural sphere, art project, directing of art projects.

1. Introduction

The problem formulation. Modern Ukrainian society is in dire need of highly qualified leaders, managers with a high level of competence, who must creatively solve strategic, operational and socio-cultural problems. Education in the socio-cultural sphere requires regular change, creative and innovative technologies appear which provide answers to the needs of society, with the help of which the personality of the future specialist is formed. Due to the fact that the specific feature of directing, screenwriting and performance, associated with the analysis, design and implementation of various projects, this aspect of activity has the ability to influence the formation of a certain worldview, promote values, and acquire professional knowledge and skills. In determining the problem area of research should focus on the introduction of the discipline “Directing art Projects” in the process of training the future manager of the socio-cultural sphere.

So the relevance of this topic is due to the wide possibilities of directing art in modern educational practice and its insufficient use in the educational and creative process by students of art institutions of higher education studying in the specialty 028 “Management of Socio-Cultural Activities”.

State study of the problem. The introduction of technology in the creation of various courses, disciplines for managers of socio-cultural activities has been studied by many scientists. In particular, in the article N. Bakhmat (2019) didactic principles and modern requirements for designing the educational process of future manager’s socio-cultural activities in the information and educational environment of higher education are considered. The modern requirements to the content of training are analyzed and the list of general cultural competences is offered taking into account didactic principles of designing educational process. M. Bryl (2018) reveals the impact of effectively organized educational and practical activities on self-development and the formation of the manager socio-cultural activities as a subject of innovation. The author recommends introducing at the level of forms and methods of teaching effective modern ideas for the formation of innovative thinking in the manager. T. Hryhorchuk (2019) focused on issues related to the design of educational and methodological complex for distance learning of future managers of the socio-cultural sphere. S. Kalaur and O. Soroka (2019) focused on the potential of a systematic approach, which provides for the unity of psychological and pedagogical theory, methodology and practice in the training of future managers socio-cultural activities. In Article O. Kostiuchenko (2017) the properties of modern training managers, factors its efficiency, in particular key elements, principles, functions of project training are analyzed. Attention is

focused on the properties of relevant training, which require the development and implementation of the following technologies: full-fledged mentoring for everyone; modeling and forecasting of individual learning trajectory, training protocols, etc. V. Liubarets (2018) considered modern requirements for the content of training manager of socio-cultural activities due, on the one hand, trends in society and its spiritual sphere, and on the other – regulations governing the order and content of the educational process.

Among the scientists who consider technology in the management of socio-cultural activities should be noted work S. Kostylev (2014), Ya. Martynyshyn, Ye. Kovalenko (2018), G. Novikova (2006), where the specifics and significance of modern management as a complex system of principles, functions, methods in the structure of socio-cultural management, aimed at the formation, functioning and development of artistic and creative space, providing production, reproduction and translation of artistic ideals, sample, values and practices.

In the context of our work, aspects of project management are explored R. D. Archibald (2017), which focuses on the implementation of project portfolio management concepts and project management organizations in the company by creating project offices.

K. Davydovskiy (2014) formulates the parameters of the art project and distinguishes between educational and extracurricular art projects of educational institutions. M. Poplavskiy (2019) characterizes the phenomenon of project activity – “crossover point” and its spread in modern art practice. The author notes the growing mass demand for entertainment and musical theatrical projects as a new form of synthesis of several arts, generated by the implementation of new technologies.

The use of directing in the context of professional training of future professionals in their work explores, in particular: E. Dolgireva (2012) considering directing as a basic didactic technology of socio-cultural activities. Under the direction of socio-cultural activities means applied didactic technology, which can procedurally provide socio-cultural production and technologically make the transition of socio-cultural pedagogical technologies from scientific and procedural-descriptive to procedurally effective personal level. In Article V. Mozghoviy (2014) modern approaches to the use of directing tools, the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities in the context of professional training in the system of higher education institutions are analyzed.

Unresolved issues. Noting the importance of scientific research of these scientists, it should be emphasized that in this problem today there are still many unresolved issues. Today the methodology of managing cultural and artistic projects is widely used in the socio-cultural sphere. The modern manager

of the socio-cultural sphere is constantly working in an environment where he becomes a subject of activity. The problem of training the future manager of socio-cultural activities by means of directing, both in theoretical and in practical terms, deserves constructive attention. In particular, further requires the importance of directing art projects in the acquisition of professional knowledge and professional skills, which allows to addition the nature of the activity, promotes personal development, identifies and forms the value competencies of the future manager socio-cultural sphere.

So the lack of elaboration of the problem of implementation directing art projects in the system of training the future manager socio-cultural sphere determined the purpose and methods of this research.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose of the study. The purpose of the article is to identify and generalize current trends in the use of the discipline “Directing Art Projects” in the development of professional knowledge and skills in the training of future competitive managers who will be active and qualified in socio-cultural sphere.

The methodological basis of the study. The methodological basis of the research is dialectical ideas about the relationship between theory and practice in the study of socio-cultural phenomena and processes. The fundamental provisions of this work are based on the competence approach, which defines artistic and creative skills as an integral part of the professional training of the future manager of socio-cultural activities; on an innovative approach, which involves awareness of the need to implement modern creative trends in the organization of the educational process of students in accordance with the specifics and direction of education; on a systematic approach that identifies ways to involve future managers of socio-cultural activities in the creation of creative cultural and artistic projects through the combination of theory and practice of management and content directing art projects; on culturological and activity approaches, which emphasize the formation of the personality of the future manager of socio-cultural activities in the system of higher education institutions.

Research methods. The research uses methods of analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, comparison and comparison, specific scientific and empirical methods, according to which the structure of the discipline is proposed in the relationship of its main elements and specific factors important for training socio-cultural managers. The method of analysis provided us with opportunities to identify the place of the means of directing in the practical work of the future manager socio-cultural sphere. Through synthesis, we were able to find a relationship between the use of techniques for directing art

projects in the system of art institutions of higher education. Induction and deduction are to highlight the features of professional training of future managers. Comparison and comparison – to identify common and different terminological concepts in the context of artistic practice; the use of a systematic approach allowed us to conclude that directing art projects allows to prepare students majoring in “Management of Socio-Cultural Activities” with certain qualities and practical skills, able not only to skillfully use the experience of their profession, but also to actively enrich it with new professional knowledge. There is promoting the development of value competencies. Empirical methods: conversations, dialogues, surveys, questionnaires, conferences (on-line in the “ZOOM” system) with faculty and students focused the author on organizational, scientific, methodological, theoretical issues of this research topic.

Research information base. The information base of the study consists of the analysis results of publications of leading scientists and researchers in the socio-cultural sphere on the design of the process of training future managers of socio-cultural activities in the artistic institution of higher education. The study also used the data of personal observations of the author, made during the teaching of professionally-oriented disciplines in the specialty 028 “Management of Socio-Cultural Activities” at the Department of Show Business Management at the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts (Ukraine).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Prerequisites for the formation of competencies of managers of the socio-cultural sphere

In the socio-cultural sphere, project forms of cultural and artistic activity have become widespread. In particular, *Mykhailo Poplavskyi* (2019) describing the phenomenon of project activity (“crossover point”) takes the view that the term “project”, borrowed from technical disciplines in the practice of the art market, it has acquired a new meaning: it is not only a plan but also a plan, preparation and implementation in various formats “Work of Art. So the etymology of the word sometimes comprehensively reproduces the basic meanings of existence ...” (p. 251). According to the English Association of Project Managers, a project is “a separate enterprise with defined goals that take into account the requirements for time, cost and quality of results achieved” (Project Management Institute, 2000, p. 12). In the British standard BS 6079-1: 2000, the term “project” is defined as “a unique set of coordinated actions (works) with a specific beginning and end, carried out by a particular person or enterprise to achieve the goal in a predetermined time, cost and performance parameters”

(British Standards Institution, 1996, p. 4). *Russel Archibald* (2017) defines the project as “a set of efforts to achieve certain unique results within the allotted time and within an agreed budget allocated to finance the resources used during the project implementation” (p. 18).

So from the above definitions it is possible to draw a conclusion about the features that are common to all projects: focus on achieving specific goals; coordinated implementation of certain agreed actions; time and resource constraints; the uniqueness of the idea and the implementation of the plan, which is carried out by a particular person or organization, i.e. the project team.

If we describe socio-cultural activities, and we qualify it as a process aimed at creating an environment where project technologies are used, which, in turn, meet the specific needs of a person or group of people in communication, culture, art, creativity, leisure, and matter not only for the individual, but for society as a whole. *Galina Novikova* (2006) emphasizes, “that socio-cultural technologies are pedagogical systems of sequential algorithmic organizational and managerial actions, the functioning of personal, instrumental and methodological tools aimed at achieving the planned results” (p. 13). *Sergei Kostylev* (2014) offers the following types in the classification of sociocultural technologies: “organizational and administrative; marketing; educational and vocational oriented; creatively developing, shaping; communicative; advertising and public relations; event technologies; publicity technologies”. *Olena Kostiuchenko* (2017) notes that “a factor of success in the management of project activities, which aims to implement the project with maximum efficiency with given constraints on time, resources and quality of the final results is the formation of a holistic system of professional readiness of the future manager of socio-cultural sphere” (p. 40).

Thus, the creative and commercial success of projects in the socio-cultural sphere largely depends on effective leadership, developed strategy, setting real goals and objectives, making optimal decisions, market research, competitiveness, recruitment.

Socio-cultural management today is considered as one of the functional role activities associated with the processes of selection, storage, production and dissemination of cultural values. The functions of the manager of socio-cultural sphere have a number of features that are manifested in the content of activities, which allows the use of technology, cooperation, financial resources, competition methods, innovative, creative mechanisms for managing product production in the cultural services market. According to *Nataliia Bakhmat* (2019), “the model of professional training of a manager of socio-cultural activities that performs (social, communicative, professional, integrative, social, economic,

culturological functions) should contain the following components: motivational, meaningful, procedural, scientific-methodical, evaluative-effective and ensures expressed through integrated continuity and completeness the process of forming professionalism of activity, and differentiated knowledge, ways of professional activity” (p. 20). “For the current generation of leaders”, says *Maryna Bryl* (2018), “it becomes important to have a vague, interactive, creatively constructive, systematic thinking that can be called positive and correct, that overcomes the obstacles and barriers we set for ourselves, and which arise in a world where chaos and disorder are more common. The task of the manager is to form resources to encourage both group and individual creativity, the source of which in psychological management is professional reflection and self-development” (p. 51).

In the vision of *Svitlana Kalaur* and *Olha Soroka* (2019), the introduction of a systematic approach, “primarily due to the urgent need to make radical changes in its priorities, which in a practical sense involves overcoming formalism in learning and independence in cognitive activity of students majoring in management socio-cultural activities” (p. 238).

So management technologies in the activities of the manager socio-cultural sphere are manifested in the fact that:

- 1) the essence of the manager allows you to use a wide range of types and forms of management;
- 2) basis of mutual interest cooperation is carried out and opportunities of various material, technical, personnel and financial resources are involved;
- 3) methods of competition for the implementation of commercial and social projects to obtain budgetary and extra budgetary funds;
- 4) search for new innovative, creative mechanisms of activity is carried out and new knowledge and skills in the field of project management, economic components and legal relations are acquired.

However, project technologies in the socio-cultural sphere have a number of properties specific to this type of creative activity. The term “project” “in the context of artistic practice is understood not only as a result of the original plan, but as a unique set of coordinated actions aimed at achieving a specific cultural, aesthetic and artistic goal” (*Poplavskyi*, 2019, p. 253).

In the study of the concept of “art project” *Kostiantyn Davydovskiy* (2014) determines a number of parameters and features: the birth of a new progressive artistic idea; availability of favorable conditions for the introduction of new artistic initiatives; creating a precedent of historical “excess” – the publication of a previously unknown but significant fact that can interest the cultural and artistic environment, or the birth of a fundamentally new,

relevant and modern concept of cultural event; presence of an art project leader; definition of a clear (namely artistic direction) goals and objectives of the project; determination (choice) of a certain time for the event, which is repeated periodically and due to the most favorable circumstances, especially – social; formation of own audience of a long art project; support of the art project by the relevant authorities; diversification of sources of funding for an art project; for the long-term existence of the art project it is necessary to create a public and international resonance of the first event of the project, its wide publicity in the media (pp. 109-110).

So an art project is a kind of response to the “social order” of society, a response in artistic form to a particular social phenomenon. The developed art project helps the manager of the socio-cultural sphere to avoid many inaccuracies in its implementation. It flexibly combines creative, technical, financial and market aspects of activity. *Vladyslava Liubarets* (2018) emphasizes “modern requirements for the content of training manager of socio-cultural activities, due, on the one hand, trends in society and its spiritual sphere, and on the other – regulations governing the order and content of the educational process for managers in the socio-cultural sphere” (p. 12).

All this allows us to conclude that: future managers of the socio-cultural sphere must confidently navigate in today's social space of current needs, evaluate and draw up business plans, product promotion strategy, or orient the market to their individual values; analyze information materials, be able to turn information into business or public projects, applying the principles of formation, operation of the management system, professional experience, technology, finance and legal components for the development of the organization, as well as use directing technologies in the implementation of artistic project.

3.2. Directing technologies in the training of a socio-cultural manager

On the example of the discipline “Directing art Projects” we will try to explore in more detail the role of modern directing technologies in the professional training of the future manager of the socio-cultural sphere.

Second-year students of the Department of Show Business, Faculty of Event Management and Show Business of the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts have the opportunity to study two semesters of the discipline “Directing Art Projects”. As indicated *Taras Hryhorchuk* (2019) “the model of the discipline is determined by the subject, methods, purpose and objectives of its research. Here, knowledge and skills are declared, and in the case of practice-oriented courses – professional competencies that are acquired

in the process of mastering the program requirements (lecture material, practical tasks, testing, acquaintance with information sources)” (p. 29).

The purpose of studying the discipline: providing students, future managers of socio-cultural activities, the necessary knowledge of the basics of directing and skills for professional management of the organization and implementation of art projects.

Note the task of the discipline is the formation of theoretical knowledge on the organization and conduct of art projects in the socio-cultural sphere, explanation and disclosure of the system of the director, as well as the application of knowledge during practical work. Upon mastering the discipline, the student must know:

- basic methods of work and specific features of directing, screenwriting and performance creativity in the organization and conduct of art projects;
- practical bases of work on creation of art projects in the field of show business;
- psychological and pedagogical mechanisms of emotional influence on spectators and participants of art projects;
- the synthetic nature of art projects, which includes various types and genres of artistic creativity.

Based on the “social order” the student must be able to:

- analyze and in an emotional and figurative form to formulate the director's idea of the future production of an art project;
- develop an original script and director's score of the project, which should reflect the director's move, figurative solution;
- have the methods of director's analysis, the laws of composition, technology and use them in production activities;
- use as a creative method different types and methods of installation;
- realize his artistic idea both in the script work and in the staging process of creating an art project.

When studying the discipline “Directing Art Projects” at the Department of Show Business of the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, students in the form of lectures (22 hours) and practical (60 hours) master the necessary knowledge, in individual and independent (98 hours) forms of self-preparation acquired knowledge and skills of working with art events; get acquainted with educational and methodical support, literature on directing, visual video materials. The discipline has six ECTS credits. The total number of hours is 180. The final control is carried out at the end of the semester. The form of final control is a test and an exam.

Interdisciplinary links: the normative discipline “Directing Art Projects” is based on the humanities and socio-cultural disciplines: “Theory and History of Culture”, “Fundamentals of Management”, “Philosophy”, “Psychology”, “Management of Socio-Cultural Activities”. Knowledge of the discipline “Directing art Projects” is used in the study “Management in Show Business”, “Model Business Management”, “Event Management” is further transformed into “Project Management of Socio-Cultural Activities» (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The place of directing art projects in the system of formation of professional competencies of the manager of socio-cultural activity

Source: own development

The training course “Directing art Projects” forms in future specialists managers of socio-cultural sphere: value competencies necessary for the rational use of tools and modern directing technologies during practical classes: identification of features of the art project; formulation of a project idea; creation of the project concept and stages of its development; justification of project effectiveness, as before the project study; interests students with opportunities for development in the field of culture and art; creates preconditions for creative self-realization of each student.

The first stage is dominated by the active adaptation of students of future managers of socio-cultural activities to the basics of directing. The purpose and tasks of the discipline are realized, the theoretical bases of directing art projects are considered: the concept and essence of the category “art”: basic aspects and problems of modern understanding; the art project is analyzed

as a form of organization of sociocultural activity and the specifics of directing art projects.

The second stage is aimed at the active mastering of the drama of art projects, where students consider the features of the drama of art projects, gain practical experience in developing a script and stages of its development; learn to use the script as the basis of an art project. The analysis of the material gives an opportunity to understand more deeply the ideological and artistic features of the script, to set a clearer task for the performers.

The third stage consists in a workshop: where the director's analysis of the art project is noted; the idea and documentation of the project, their role in the creative process of the director and the technology of implementation of the director's idea of the art project.

Director's analysis of an art project is the initial and one of the main stages of the director's work to create a future stage work, the creative process of cognition of dramatic material, analysis of its main elements. The director's idea is a creative process, as a result of which a concrete understanding and comprehension of reality must be formed, which will determine the plastic-spatial and tonal solution of the project in a single stylistic and genre plane based on the concept interpreted by the director. By directing the creative activity of all participants in the collective work on the stage embodiment, the director achieves on the basis of his creative idea.

So the laws of composition in an art project, formed in the process of artistic understanding of reality, to some extent reflect the objective laws of the real world. These patterns are figurative, associated with the specifics of a particular art form, artistic idea and the material of the work, which reflects the aesthetic principles of the era, style and artistic direction are based on the analysis, design and implementation of the art project.

The prospects for the spread of activity-oriented pedagogical education prompted *Viktor Mozghoyi* (2014) to analyze this approach in more detail in the context of training future professionals by means of directing pedagogical action. Summarizing the results of the study, the author concludes that the established variability of approaches to the use of the basics of directing in the training of future teachers is one of the ways to address the demands of modern pedagogical practice (p. 213). *Elena Dolgireva* (2012) emphasizes that “the universality of mechanisms of influence and formation allows us to consider the direction of socio-cultural activities as a basic didactic technology that can provide with a subtle psychologically justified touch to the individual real socio-cultural interaction of subjects with the world, and acts as a decisive factor in the formation of professional and pedagogical techniques” (p. 43).

So directing art projects in the modern system of training of the future manager of the socio-cultural sphere is considered as a means of his professional development, given that:

- increased interest in the discipline, which is taught with the use of directing technologies; it becomes more objective, modern; it is a universal form of artistic and stage modeling, creative project activity created by means of socio-cultural activity;

- the discipline allows to involve students in active educational and cognitive activities, creative situations that require concentration, activation of creative imagination in the formulation of the author's attitude to the script problem and the image-emotional content of the future work of art;

- the results of practical work, it is taking into account the artistic, creative and technical capabilities on the stage; mandatory implementation of the plan, where the manager must prove himself as a specialist who methodically adheres to the basic requirements of the implementation of the art project;

- increasing the percentage of students who wish to continue working with directing technologies in socio-cultural activities, usually increases the quality of education.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the above-described classes in directing art projects in no way deny the traditional classes in the management of socio-cultural activities, cannot replace them, but complement them and contribute to their effectiveness and competence: practical skills, willingness to implement their directing plan, both when writing a dramatic basis (script) and in the process of creating art projects; ability to work with colleagues and partners, the ability to solve problems in different life situations; communication skills, free and confident use of professional terminology; ability to set and solve applied problems using the theory and practice of modern directing art projects; adaptability, skills to develop long-term action plans, intrinsic motivation, the ability to make their own choices and set personal goals.

4. Conclusions

The article formulates the results of a study on the introduction of innovations in the educational process of professional training of future managers of socio-cultural activities. Generalization of modern trends in the educational environment of higher education institutions allows us to draw the following conclusions:

1. Directing art projects in the modern system of training the future manager of socio-cultural sphere is considered as a means of professional development, given that: it is an activity based on creative organization of artistic production, designed to create conditions for effective implementation of values in Ukrainian society.

2. The use of modern directing technologies in teaching significantly complements the traditional views on teaching methods, structure and organization of educational activities, makes teaching subjects more interesting, meaningful, visual.

3. Directing art projects allows preparing students majoring in socio-cultural management with certain qualities and practical skills, able not only to skillfully use the experience of their profession, but also to actively enrich it with new professional knowledge, promoting the development of valuable competencies, provides opportunities for creative ideas. Changing the role of the student from a passive listener to an active-creative, independent participant in the process.

Scientific novelty of the obtained results. The scientific novelty lies in the application of systematic and methodological-didactic approaches to updating the content of professional training of future managers of socio-cultural activities in the educational environment of the discipline “Directing Art Projects”. Scientific provisions on the importance of directing in the acquisition of professional knowledge and professional skills, which allow filling the process of activity with artistic and creative content, promote personal development, identify and form the value orientations of the future manager socio-cultural sphere.

The practical significance of the results obtained. The practical significance of the results is revealed in the possibility of their use to solve a number of theoretical problems and develop recommendations for the use of modern directing technologies in the process of curricula, programs, directing training tools, development of methodological materials, practical staging activities in the educational process institutions of higher education.

Prospects for further scientific exploration in this direction. It is promising to research conditions of the favorable environment of the institution of higher education in which the formation of the future manager of socio-cultural activities by means of directing art projects.

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References:

- Archibald, R. D. (2017). *Upravlenie Vysokotekhnologichnymi Programmami i Proektami [Managing High-Technology Programs and Project]* (E. Mamontov, Trans. in Eng.). Moscow: DMK Press (in Russ.).
- Bakhmat, N. (2019). Proektuvannia Protsesu Pidhotovky Majbutnikh Menedzheriv Sotsiokul'turnoi Diial'nosti v Umovakh Informatsijno-Osvitn'oho Seredovyscha Zakladu Vyschoi Osvity [Designing the Process of Training Future Managers of Social and Cultural Activities in the Information and Educational Environment of Higher Education]. *Psykhologo-Pedahohichni Problemy Suchasnoi Shkoly [Psychological and Pedagogical Problems of Modern School]*, 2, 14-21, doi: <https://doi.org/10.31499/2706-6258.2.2019.178451> (in Ukr.).
- British Standards Institution (1996). *Project Management. Guide to Project Management (BS 6079-1:2000)*. London: BSI.
- Bryl, M. (2018). Menedzher Sotsiokul'turnoi Diial'nosti iak Subiekt Innovatsij [Manager of Social and Cultural Activity as a Subject of Innovations]. *Visnyk Kyivs'koho Natsional'noho Universytetu Kul'tury i Mystetstv. Seriia: Menedzhment Sotsiokul'turnoi Diial'nosti [Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Management of Social and Cultural Activity]*, 1, 41-52, doi: <https://doi.org/10.31866/2616-7573.1.2018.143386> (in Ukr.).
- Davydovskyi, K. (2014). Mystets'kyj Proekt u Suchasnij Sotsiokul'turnij Real'nosti Ukrainy (Dosvid Tvorchykh Initsiatyv Kyivs'koho Instytutu Muzyky im. R. M. Hliiera) [Art Project in the Modern Social and Cultural Reality of Ukraine (Experience of Creative Initiatives of the R. Glier Kyiv Institute of Music)]. *Mystetstvoznavchi Zapysky [Notes on Art Criticism]*, 25, 106-113 (in Ukr.).
- Dolgireva, E. (2012). Rezhissura kak Bazovaya Didakticheskaya Tekhnologiya Sotsial'no-Kul'turnoy Deyatel'nosti [Directing as a Basic Didactic Technology of Social and Cultural Activity]. *Srednee Professional'noe Obrazovanie [Secondary Vocational Education]*, 1, 39-44 (in Russ.).
- Hryhorchuk, T. (2019). Poperednie Proektuvannia Navchal'no-Metodychnoho Kompleksu dlia Dystantsijnoho Navchannia Majbutnikh Menedzheriv Sotsiokul'turnoi Sfery [Preliminary Design of Educational and Methodical Complex for Distance Learning of Future Managers of Social and Cultural Sphere]. *Sotsial'no-Humanitarnyj Visnyk [Social and Humanitarian Bulletin]*, 26-27, 26-29 (in Ukr.).
- Kalaur, S., & Soroka, O. (2019). Metodolohichni ta Praktychni Aspekty Vprovadzhennia Systemnoho Pidkhodu u Profesijnu Pidhotovku Majbutnikh Menedzheriv Sotsiokul'turnoi Diial'nosti [Methodological and Practical Aspects of Implementing a Systematic Approach in the Training of Future Managers of Social and Cultural Activities]. *Pedahohichni Nauky: Teoriia, Istoriia, Innovatsijni Tekhnologii [Pedagogical Sciences: Theory, History, Innovative Technologies]*, 8(92), 229-238, doi: <https://doi.org/10.24139/2312-5993/2019.08/229-238> (in Ukr.).

- Kostiuchenko, O. (2017). Tvorchyj i Adaptyvnyj Potentsial Navchannia Menedzheriv Sotsiokul'turnoi Sfery [Creative and Adaptive Potential for Managerial Services in the Social and Cultural Sphere]. *Naukovyj Visnyk Khersonskoho Derzhavnogo Universytetu. Serii "Psykhologichni Nauky" [Scientific Bulletin of Kherson State University. Series "Psychological Sciences"]*, 3(2), 36-40 (in Ukr.).
- Kostylev, S. (2014). Tekhnolohyy Art-Menedzhmenta v Strukture Sotsyokulturnoho Tekhnolohycheskoho Kompleksa [Art Management Technologies in the Structure of the Sociocultural Technological Complex]. *Vestnik KrasGAU [Bulletin of KrasGAU]*, 1, 212-219 (in Russ.).
- Liubarets, V. (2018). *Profesijna Pidhotovka Majbutnikh Menedzheriv Sotsiokul'turnoi Diial'nosti dlia Industrii Hostynnosti: Teoretychni Obgruntuvannia [Professional Training of Future Managers of Social and Cultural Activities for the Hospitality Industry: Theoretical Justifications]*. Sumy: Universytets'ka knyha (in Ukr.).
- Martynshyn, Ya. M., & Kovalenko, Ye. Ya. (2018). Formuvannia Suchasnoi Systemy Upravlinnia Zhyttiediial'nistiu Suspil'stva [Formation of the Modern System Management of Life Society]. *Visnyk Kyivs'koho Natsional'noho Universytetu Kul'tury i Mystetstv. Serii: Menedzhment Sotsiokul'turnoi Diial'nosti [Bulletin of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts. Series in Management of Social and Cultural Activity]*, 1, 7-24, doi: <https://doi.org/10.31866/2616-7573.1.2018.143383> (in Ukr.).
- Mozghovyi, V. (2014). Rezhysura Pedahohichnoi Dii u Konteksti Profesijnoi Pidhotovky Majbutnikh Uchyteliv [Directing Pedagogical Action in the Context of Professional Training of Future Teachers]. *Vytoky Pedahohichnoi Majsternosti. Serii "Pedahohichni Nauky" [The Sources of Pedagogical Skills. Series "Pedagogical Sciences"]*, 13, 209 (in Ukr.).
- Novikova, G. (2006). *Tekhnologii Art-Menedzhmenta [Art Management Technologies]*. Moscow: MGUKI (in Russ.).
- Poplavskiy, M. (2019). Mystets'kyj Proekt: Dyskurs Khudozhn'oi Kul'tury Pochatku Novoho Tysiacholittia (u Tochtsi Peretynu – Crossover Point) [Art Project: the Discourse of Artistic Culture of the Beginning of the New Millennium (at the Point of Intersection – Crossover Point)]. *Visnyk Natsional'noi Akademii Kerivnykh Kadriv Kul'tury i Mystetstv [National Academy of Managerial Staff of Culture and Arts Herald]*, 1, 248-254 (in Ukr.).
- Project Management Institute (2000). *A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge*. Newtown Square, PA: Project Management Institute.

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